

A lorry by any other name

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Abstract

The Australian War Memorial's design concept for the upgrade of its Second World War galleries included the display of the Chevrolet 3-ton lorry in its collection. This lorry was needed to represent a campaign in North Africa, but it had served in Australia, so it retained its original jungle green finish, not the sand colour used in North Africa. Preparation of the vehicle for the new display would require the removal of major components, the application of a protective barrier layer, overpainting in the North African sand colour, and the fabrication of new fittings. Senior management were approached to consider placing the lorry on display in its original finish, accompanied by an explanatory text panel; but this suggestion was rejected and a directive was given to overpaint.

The limited timeframe, and lack of evidence that the barrier layer would be both effective and reversible, were points of concern. Then staff found an unprovenanced type example lorry for sale on EBay that suited the story and also presented an opportunity to avoid treatment options that were constrained by the ethics that apply to collection material. Management supported the purchase. The vehicle was not given National Collection status, but acquired as a "spare" to be disassembled and used for parts after the exhibition closed.

This process invites a range of questions:

- How to present a convincing case for change where there is a need to protect the integrity of a relic while meeting display requirements?
- Is the institution compromising the integrity of a display when the object is categorised as a spare?
- What do the general public want, what do stakeholders expect, and how do those considerations currently factor into the decision-making process?

Introduction

This paper reviews a conflict: the need to meet the requirements of historically accurate display, balanced against the need to maintain the integrity of the Australian War Memorial's collection. The Memorial wished to display a Chevrolet 3-ton lorry in the sand colour appropriate to a vehicle that had served in the North African campaigns of 1941–42; however, the Chevrolet lorry already in its collection was green. Should it be displayed in green with a text panel explaining the colour disparity, or should it be overpainted in the sand colour? An alternative approach was to purchase a lorry of a similar type without known historical significance, which staff had no ethical qualms about painting. However, this vehicle had not actually served in North Africa. What was the best course of action for the presentation? The issue raises questions about public perception and the definition of authenticity.

- How does the presentation style (conserved as found, repainted to look new, or repainted to look used) affect the visitor experience?
- How does displaying an object that “wasn't really there” have an effect on the visitor experience? Does it significantly reduce the authenticity of the display? Is it enough for visitors to gain to see an illustrative example of its type?
- The classification of an object is important in guiding its future in the collection, and indeed the future of the collection as a whole. Does it produce a short-term collection that has good display potential now but little historic value for the future?

Exhibition development

The Australian War Memorial last redeveloped the Second World War galleries in 1999. After 10 years, the displays needed rejuvenation and the lighting and audiovisual gear needed an overhaul to reduce energy usage. The institution committed 18 months to refurbishing the galleries, with a scheduled completion by mid-2010.

The design brief was to fill the first of the four galleries with large technology objects (LTOs) used in North Africa and the Mediterranean in 1940–41. The layout of the stories and the visitor flow within the gallery necessitated a complete overhaul, as the existing displays were considered to provide a broken narrative. LTOs were chosen for three

reasons: to represent stories of Australian experiences in war, to direct visitor traffic, and to keep visitors in the gallery longer.

Initial concept design for Second World War galleries half-life refurbishment

Standard exhibition development procedure at the Memorial is to identify the themes of an exhibition and interrogate the collections for objects, art, documents, and images to illustrate these themes with stories of Australian experiences. Where LTOs are identified as key objects in a display, they are a major factor in the development of the theme. In some instances, where the collections are found to be lacking, additional material, known as “exhibition fitout” is purchased to supplement displays.

The initial concept design for Gallery 1 included a Dingo Scout Car, a Pak 40, and a *Kübelwagen*. In the previous few years, and in anticipation of the gallery upgrade, a Ford Marmon Herrington Model 11T Tractor, an Artillery Trailer No. 27 Mk 1, and a 25-pounder gun combination had been restored and repainted in the sand colour used in the North African campaigns, in the expectation that as vehicles commonly used in service, they might be chosen for the gallery redevelopment. Interestingly, these vehicles provide a demonstration of the Memorial’s default position on the issue of repainting objects for display, as they either had been used in service and retained the painted finish of that time, or they had significant provenance elsewhere and were repainted to reflect another time in the object’s service history or they were unprovenanced and repainted. All of these scenarios show that the issue had come up before, but this was perhaps the first time the Memorial had explicitly discussed it and addressed the philosophical implications of it.

This initial design concept was rejected, both due to repetition (a sand-coloured 25-pounder was already on display as part of a set piece in Gallery 2) and because it was considered to lack the “wow” factor. The collection was re-examined for alternatives. A Flak 38, captured by the Australians from the Germans and with its original paint, was considered, but the painted finish was in poor condition. Given past experience, the curators were concerned that, given past experience, if the objects chosen were in poor condition, a directive would be issued to repaint them, so it was proposed instead to display a 1941 jungle green Chevrolet Model 41/E22 General Service lorry, which was in good condition, although not in North African colours.

REL29548 1941 Chevrolet Model 41/E22 General Service lorry. Reproduced with permission from the Australian War Memorial.

Finding a story

The exhibition curator needed to find stories for Gallery 1 that placed the lorry in the North African campaigns. An unusual story about Australians 8 Battery, 3 Light Anti-Aircraft (LAA) Regiment using Chevrolet lorries at Tobruk was unearthed via the Memorial's Photographs collection. The capture of the Libyan port of Tobruk from the Italians had brought victory and also provided supplementary equipment for the Australians, including artillery and ammunition. An Australian, Major Philip Stokes, developed a system of attaching a captured Breda anti-aircraft gun to a vehicle to increase his troops' mobility. This combination had the gunner operating the Breda, while two men, one on either side, fed ammunition through it from feed trays. This set-up presented two dangers: men could fall off the moving vehicle, and on the open lorry they were completely exposed to attack. These soldiers were exposed to the blast zone that they would have been protected from, had they been operating the gun from a bunker.

Stokes' men's use of captured equipment led to his troops being nicknamed "Stokes' Travelling Circus". It was an example of Australian ingenuity in a time of need, and it

also provided the theme of “mobility in the desert war”. Technology curators confirmed that the Chevrolet lorry type in general was relevant to the Middle East and North Africa from mid-1941, and it could legitimately be used in the role with a Breda LAA gun (which the Memorial possessed) mounted onto the open rear tray.

Our lorry doesn't match the story

The Memorial's green lorry was a 1941 model, but a detailed examination revealed that the green lorry had different mudguards to the lorry in the photographs: they were squared at the rim, not rounded, and bigger, having been modified in accordance with Australian Military Force (AMF) requirements to clear the AMF standardised 10:50x18 tyres that were mounted on two-piece combat wheels. The Memorial's green lorry also had an Australian-manufactured cabin and a rear timber body with fixed sides. In order to get the lorry into the configuration seen in the images:

- the rear body sides would need to be dismantled and removed;
- the whole lorry would need repainting , including the wheels;
- additional components would need to be fabricated and fitted: e.g., TAC plate [tactical sign] holders, front and rear number plates, and mounts for the front bumper.

If this were to be done, Conservation recommended that:

- The original rear tray body and canopy bows be removed in a single piece from the chassis, and a new flat tray body be manufactured to replace it, thus preserving the integrity of the original body tray with fixed sides. Removal of the tray could, however, possibly damage or destroy the original bolts, timber and paintwork.
- The original paintwork and camouflage pattern underneath would require the application of an untested barrier layer, extensive infilling, and overpainting in sand colour. However, staff had limited experience in the use and efficiency of barrier layers, and such layers require extensive testing to confirm their effectiveness and reversibility before use.
- A physical barrier should be placed around the object for open display.

This approach was not what either the conservators or the curators would have preferred, because it would compromise the integrity of the vehicle. The preference of both parties, in general, has been to maintain an LTO as a whole wherever possible, for several reasons: to reduce the likelihood of unattached components being misplaced over time; to maintain originality and authenticity; and to minimise the potential for damage during treatment and display. An alternative proposal was also put forward to display the lorry with its original paint, accompanied by a text panel explaining that the vehicle was only representative of the type used in North Africa.

The Exhibitions section was happy to see the lorry presented with its original green paint with an explanatory text panel, but the fact that corporate management also wanted all LTOs to be “dressed” (fitted with relevant ancillary objects such as ammunition boxes, gun mounts, etcetera) introduced an extra complication, as fitting these items would damage the original tray. The final recommendation was the lorry should be presented in its existing green colour, but with a replica tray, which could be easily dressed.

- Corporate management were not happy with this approach, and directed that all LTOs in Gallery 1 should be painted in a colour and finish appropriate to North Africa in 1941 – this meant we needed to repaint the Chevrolet 3-ton lorry.

Efficacy of a barrier layer

If the lorry were to be repainted without destroying its green paint, which was authentic to its Australian service, the green paint would need to be protected by a barrier layer. Barrier layers had been applied to objects in the Memorial’s collection in the past but although they had been found to be reversible shortly after application, their reversibility after several years had not been tested. It was also unknown whether the barrier layer would saturate the original paint and change its appearance.

In the past, two barrier layers had been used. A barrier layer of wax had been applied to a Japanese 1934 Type 94 Tankette before overpainting. Although the overpainted layer was easily removed when the surface was scratched with a fingernail, the process risked irreversible saturation of the original paint. This presented something of a paradox though – although the overpaint on the tankette was easily removed to restore its original appearance, management had stipulated that all the LTOs in the new Second

World War display would be on open display, which meant that similar overpaint on the lorry would be likely to be removed by the public touching the vehicle. Testing had also not been done to determine what would happen when the barrier layer was removed from larger areas.

In another previous treatment of an LTO, gum arabic had been applied over the non-original squadron markings on the Memorial's Lockheed Hudson Mk IV bomber. The gum arabic was more robust, but its reversibility had not been tested.

Overpainting would also require extensive surface preparation prior to application of the barrier layer. The deadlines were very tight and there was little time for either testing or surface preparation. Decisions needed to be made.

Another lorry

The “Ebay” lorry. Reproduced with permission from the Australian War Memorial.

In a serendipitous set of circumstances, Large Technology Conservation staff found a lorry on EBay that fulfilled some of the exhibition requirements. The potential benefits of purchasing the EBay lorry would be:

- It was closer in configuration to the lorry in the photographs than the lorry held in the collection. Although the tray was in poor condition, it could be refabricated in-house.
- Concerns about overpainting would not be an issue, because the lorry had no known provenance and would not be accessioned as part of the National Collection (it would be classified as a “spare”, “prop” or “exhibition fitout”). This would allow conservators to avoid the ethical constraints that went with National Collection status, potentially saving hundreds of hours of conservation work.
- Concerns about the object being on open display without a physical barrier would not be an issue, again because the lorry would not be accessioned as part of the National Collection.

The curators, conservators, Exhibitions section and management all agreed that the purchase of the EBay lorry would alleviate the practical concerns: the original paint layer on the provenanced lorry would not be overpainted, hundreds of treatment hours would be avoided, and the resulting vehicle would be visually closer to the vehicle in the photograph. The vehicle was accordingly purchased, prepared and placed on display in time to meet the exhibition deadline.

Practical concerns such as these often rule in the tight timelines before an exhibition. In the months following the acquisition of the vehicle, however, philosophical questions of authenticity and interpretation have been canvassed, and it is these we will explore in the rest of the paper. The questions we will address are:

1. What impact would the use of a lorry that had no known provenance, let alone provenance from North Africa, have on the integrity of the display?
2. Would visitors, seeing a vehicle that looked freshly painted, feel that it lacked authenticity?
3. Was there potential for visitors to take away the false impression that the vehicle on display had actually served in North Africa, and did it matter if they did?
4. And finally, would the purchase of an unprovenanced vehicle for display start a trend of acquiring objects for short-term display goals, which would ultimately degrade the cultural value of the wider collection?

Public expectations and the integrity of a display

1. What impact would the use of a lorry that had no known provenance, let alone provenance from North Africa, have on the integrity of the display?

An American study of the ways in which people use and engage with the past more generally showed that the importance of real historic sites and objects was that people perceived them as being unmediated. They felt that such things gave them direct access to the past, and they could interrogate and evaluate them directly, using their own prior knowledge and experience as a point of comparison. Real objects had great vividness, helping people to feel that they could put themselves into the picture and experience a moment from the past “almost as it had originally been experienced”. This gave them a sense of how people in the past might have felt in similar situations and allowed them to ask what they might have done had they been there themselves.¹ Real objects offer people a sense of a bridge to the past, a way to make a spiritual connection with the people who used those objects in other times and other places.

You think of the history, and where it's been, and who else has touched it, and historically what it went through.²

Although objects of a similar type or technical specification are able to represent the technological aspects of the machinery, and the general size and look of their type, they are not able to provide the more spiritual aspects of engagement which many visitors, particularly in the commemorative atmosphere of the Memorial, are seeking.

2. Would visitors, seeing a vehicle that looked freshly painted, feel that it lacked authenticity?

If the object is displayed with accurate but freshly repainted colours and markings, does this represent, as Andrew Whitmarsh suggests, a sanitized version of the object?

The museum's interpretation of technology can also play a part in creating a sanitised version of the past, and its portrayal of former enemies can reinforce wartime attitudes, both of which are part of traditional patterns of commemoration.”³

¹ Roy Rosenzweig and David Thelen, *The presence of the past: popular uses of history in American life*, Columbia University Press, New York, c. 1998.

² A visitor to the AWM made this comment during an interview conducted by Alison Wain for a PhD thesis in progress, Australian National University, Canberra, 2010. The interviewee was AWM283: male, 46–55, stage manager.

Ian MacLeod, of the Western Australian Museum, takes the view that if an object is to be repainted, for whatever reason, it is being repainted anyway, so it is quite legitimate to put on a coat of paint that looks as though it has been aged rather than one that looks as though it is new.⁴ Certainly, while it is often assumed that visitors want to see large technology objects looking new and freshly painted, in a recent independent study that surveyed visitors' attitudes to large technology heritage at several museum sites, including the Memorial, showed that this was not necessarily the case.⁵ Participants in the study were asked, "Do you like to see these objects restored to look new?" and most visitors, especially at the Memorial, answered "no": 79% of visitors interviewed at the Memorial did not want to see such objects looking new, as did 71% of visitors to all sites in the study.

In fact, many visitors spoke vehemently of how disappointed they would be if the objects *were* restored to look new, as it was their aged appearance which made visitors feel that the objects were real, trustworthy, and evocative. In this search for direct experience, the less restored an object was, the less its veracity was felt to have been altered and diluted by others.

This finding was borne out by comments about why visitors did not want to see objects restored, although there were subtle variations in the benefits visitors perceived in being able to see unrestored objects. Some visitors felt that an aged appearance enabled them to imagine and connect with the past:

You get an idea of how close the pilot came to death when you see all the machine-gun marks and the bullets.⁶

I prefer it when they look old. Because [if it is restored] I don't know whether it is real.⁷

³ Andrew Whitmarsh, "We will remember them - memory and commemoration in war museums", MA in Museum Studies, 2000, Institute of Archaeology, University College London

⁴ Interview with Ian MacLeod conducted in 2008 by Alison Wain for a PhD thesis in progress, Australian National University, Canberra, 2010. See note 2.

⁵ Interview conducted by Alison Wain for PhD thesis in progress, Australian National University, Canberra, 2010

⁶ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM266: female, 46–55, ferry master.

⁷ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM300: female: 19–25, tourism student from Austria.

Other visitors felt that an aged appearance made them feel that the object was a source of knowledge they could trust:

Don't paint over it for heaven's sake ... It's a museum after all, it's not an artistic place. It doesn't have to be spotless and clean and beautifully presented ... They should remain genuine rather than pretty.⁸

For a considerable number of visitors, large technology objects clearly had an anthropomorphic aspect: they felt that the object was a living entity with which they could empathise. These people saw the marks of age as honourable evidence of the object's hard-working life and achievements:

Restored as new they don't look as if they've done it. Being nice and shiny – well it hasn't done anything yet.⁹

Some felt that making objects look new was not appropriate for a historic site such as the Memorial:

The karma here is “war is hell” and so fixing them up and painting over everything isn't as appropriate.¹⁰

And many visitors felt that objects should be made to look as they would have done in service. They should not look like a wreck, but they should not look too new either:

I think they should just be kept. Maintained, as they are, like old paintings, not looking like they were painted yesterday. Preserved as best they can.¹¹

I'd like to see them restored but to their old condition if you know what I mean. So that it looks like it was just brought from Vietnam

⁸ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM281: male, >65, printer.

⁹ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM316: male, 56–65, store person.

¹⁰ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM 297: male, >65, university teacher

¹¹ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM249: female, 26–35, childcare worker.

and placed here. Not straight from an aircraft factory. If it's got holes in it I wouldn't patch them up. But clean it up a bit ...¹²

The Messerschmitt 109: seeing that in its original paintwork was more interesting than seeing it all spruced up and shiny. It's more as it was when it was in use.¹³

To restore the surface of an object to make it look new was, for many people, to deny the object's history and to show disrespect to both the object and the people who had worked so hard using it:

In the museum I don't think [restoration is] really relevant. Maybe it would be nice to have a comparative one that's new or restored as against one that's actually been in a battle, but seeing them [as they] came back from battle, I think it's a bit more grounding. Has more of an emotional impact, you can understand or appreciate a little bit more what the armed forces have to achieve, the troops. I guess if you were a collector, then you might see it a little bit differently, but this is a museum showcasing our history, and to restore something so beautifully then changes the meaning of that object.¹⁴

Visitors' interest in history generally was overwhelming: 91% of visitors at all sites, and 99% at the Memorial, said they liked to have information about the history of the large technology objects they were looking at. From their responses to the question about restoration, it seems that one source many of them look to for historical information is the visible, physical evidence of wear and tear on the object itself.

3. Was there potential for visitors to take away the false impression that the vehicle on display had actually served in North Africa, and did it matter if they did?

¹² Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM251: male, 19–25, retail salesperson.

¹³ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM259: male, 56–65, insurance broker.

¹⁴ Interview conducted for PhD study. See note 2. AWM305: female, 36–45, artist and art teacher.

As a general rule, the Memorial does not provide information in its display text about how objects have been prepared for display, except for occasional presentations by museum staff. Due to the time constraints of most exhibition development projects, the process of confirming original paint colour, the placement and type of markings, the preservation of the original surface, and the ethics involved in this process are not generally discussed with anyone outside the exhibition team. The public therefore remains largely unaware of the intense discussions that inform these decisions; they are simply presented with the final product. What do they actually want, and how do they interpret the results of our deliberations?

The text panel for the lorry is as follows:

Chevrolet lorry

The desert war was one of movement. During 1941, this was fast and fluid as the battle front moved back and forth along the coast of North Africa. The combatants used a variety of vehicles to move troops as well as to carry supplies and equipment, along the hot, dusty roads of Libya, Egypt, and Syria.

This Chevrolet was the type of general service lorry that saw extensive service with Australian forces in the Middle East. They were also used in Malaya. Modified vehicles also served in Australia and Papua, mainly around Port Moresby, until they were later replaced by purpose-built Canadian and American vehicles. [SP01542]

Chevrolet 1941 Model 41/E22 General Service lorry

Manufacturer	Chevrolet
Country of origin	USA; Australia
Year	1941
Crew	1 driver
Engine	in-line 6-cylinder

The text panel states that the Chevrolet lorry is of the type used in service in North Africa; it does not say that this particular vehicle was used in North Africa. While there is no intention to deceive, visitors could draw the conclusion that the vehicle had been used in North Africa. They might reason that all the objects in the display were likely to have had a history of service in the area or conflict discussed in the display, or they might assume that the North African paint scheme was original to the object. The

institution has a duty of care to ensure that visitors go away with an accurate message and understanding of the display.¹⁵ Further research is therefore needed to establish the messages that visitors take from this display, and whether they understand that the lorry is only representative of the type used in North Africa, and not an object that actually served there.

4. And finally, would the purchase of an unprovenanced vehicle for display start a trend of acquiring objects for short-term display goals which would ultimately degrade the cultural value of the wider collection?

The Memorial uses separate classification systems for objects that form parts of its collection and display holdings. They are as follows:

NATIONAL COLLECTION – objects that meet the requirements of the Memorial’s Collection Development Plan, including the criteria that they must have significance to Australian military history (or fill an identified gap in the collection for which no provenanced example is available); and that the benefits and resource requirements are acceptable. They must be managed to the highest standard, including full cataloguing, conservation care, and climate-controlled storage.

AWM COLLECTION – objects that, while not part of the National Collection, contribute to the goals of the Memorial in a variety of ways, for example as touch objects, or in exhibitions. They must be managed appropriately, including basic cataloguing, storage, and preventive conservation.

Prop – objects that have value but which are already represented in the collection, such as smaller Military Heraldry and Technology items, reproductions of artworks and photographs, and facsimiles of Research Centre items. They require identification, tracking, and preventive conservation.

Exhibition Fitout – objects or interpretive material used to support exhibitions. Items can be modified and disposed of after the life of the display. They require identification, tracking, and preventive conservation for the life of the display.

Spare – objects or material acquired as replacement parts for National Collection items with the designation of “Technology”. Examples include tyres, bolts, and screws. They require only bulk identification and tracking, and secure storage.

¹⁵ J. Sims in Ivan Karp, Steven D. Lavine, (eds.) “Locating Authenticity: Fragments of a Dialogue,” *Exhibiting Cultures: the poetics and politics of museum display*. Smithsonian, 1991, pp. 159-175.

The lorry was not classified as a National Collection item because it did not fulfil the requirements for this status, and because National Collection status mandated exactly the ethical concerns that we were trying to avoid. It was, in fact, classified as a "Spare", mainly because it was purchased with funding that had different usage criteria to funding used for the acquisition of collection material or exhibition development. It was also not accessioned as Exhibition Fitout because there were parts of the vehicle that had potential future uses as spares, so it would not simply be disposed of at the completion of the exhibition.

Things change, however, and there is already talk of upgrading the classification of the lorry to "Prop", or even to "National Collection". On the one hand this could be seen as taking advantage of a serendipitous find, but on the other it could be seen as an object without historical significance, which had been substantially altered for a display, slipping into the collection by the back door. The real concern with this is that, while the object was classified as a spare, it was treated and altered under a different decision-making framework to National Collection objects. In the case of the lorry this meant that: the size of the tray was reduced to fit it into the gallery, that much original material was discarded without being recorded or sampled, and that no written record was kept of the treatment process.

Certainly some tasks, such as reconstructing a condition and treatment report, and noting the changed size of the tray, could be done retrospectively if the vehicle is reclassified as National Collection, but the danger is that no-one will think to do these things, or that the people who hold this unwritten information in their heads will have forgotten the details or left the institution before the reclassification happens. This is a significant risk, as the point at which the object is reclassified is likely to be when the exhibition is renewed or replaced, which could possibly be in ten or more years' time. Another downside of reclassifying collection at a later date is the lost opportunity to collect information about the object's history from the previous owner, and in instances where the object has been conserved or modified, with treatment decisions based on a prior classification, opportunities may have been missed for investigative research.

But this would not be the first time this has been done. Collection status is quite commonly reassessed, usually when an object is chosen for an exhibition, when the catalogue record has been reviewed and the object found to fit the criteria. When significance is recognised in a previously under-appreciated object, it is probably better to save what you do have, rather than to lament what you do not.

Conclusion

This tale of two lorries goes to the heart of one of the challenges that LTOs present: they are too large and expensive to have one of every type, colour, period and use, and inevitably there will come a time when the object you have does not closely represent the story you wish to tell.

In this situation choices have to be made, and often those choices will fulfill one criteria but not another. In this case, the choices made have eased practical dilemmas, preserved the physical and historic integrity of an important object (the green lorry) for the future, and provided a display which is visually well themed and clear- all the large objects exhibited share the same colour scheme, and the lorry on display reflects the equipment configuration seen in the photographs that form the basis of the story that is being told. The criterion that could not be fulfilled is that of a spiritual connection to the past, the display of an object that actually “was there” and which has an authentic connection to the story it represents.

But hey – kicking three out of four goals is really not too bad.

SP01542 1941 Chevrolet Model 41/E22 General Service lorry, the “Ebay” lorry configured for display. Reproduced with permission from the Australian War Memorial.